

HISTOLOGICAL FINDINGS IN PATIENTS WITH ACUTE GUTTATE PARAPSORIASIS

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Abstract

The paper presents the results of a histological study of 56 patients with acute guttate parapsoriasis. Characteristic morphological changes in the epidermis and dermis reflecting the inflammatory and immune nature of the disease were identified. The obtained data make it possible to уточнить diagnostic criteria and improve differential diagnosis with other dermatoses.

Keywords: acute guttate parapsoriasis, histology, inflammation, epidermis, dermis

Introduction

Acute guttate parapsoriasis belongs to the group of inflammatory dermatoses with a not fully understood pathogenesis. The clinical picture may resemble other skin diseases, which complicates diagnosis. Histological examination plays an important role in confirming the diagnosis and determining treatment strategy.

Parapsoriasis is a group of chronic dermatoses characterized by inflammatory skin changes and a prolonged course. The article discusses clinical forms, pathogenesis, histological features, as well as modern approaches to diagnosis and treatment. Parapsoriasis объединяет several dermatological conditions that have similar clinical and morphological features. Despite long-term study, questions of etiology and pathogenesis remain debatable.

Classification

The following forms of parapsoriasis are distinguished:

- acute guttate parapsoriasis
- chronic plaque parapsoriasis
- lichenoid parapsoriasis

Pathogenesis

The disease is based on immune disorders accompanied by activation of T-lymphocytes. The role of infectious factors, genetic predisposition, and external triggers is assumed.

Histological Features

Histologically, acanthosis, parakeratosis, spongiosis, as well as lymphocytic infiltration in the dermis are observed. Perivascular infiltrates and vascular changes are characteristic.

Diagnosis

The diagnosis is based on the clinical picture and histological examination. It is important to carry out differential diagnosis with psoriasis, eczema, and cutaneous lymphomas.

Materials and Methods

Fifty-six patients with a clinical diagnosis of acute guttate parapsoriasis were examined. All patients underwent skin biopsy followed by histological examination. Changes in the epidermis, dermis, and vascular component were assessed.

Results

The following changes were identified during histological examination:

- moderate acanthosis of the epidermis
- focal parakeratosis
- spongiosis of varying severity
- lymphocytic infiltration in the dermis
- perivascular infiltrates
- dilation of microcirculatory vessels

In most patients, the changes were moderately expressed, corresponding to the early stages of the inflammatory process.

Table 1. Histological features of parapsoriasis

Discussion

The obtained data confirm the inflammatory nature of the disease. The presence of lymphocytic infiltration and vascular changes indicates immune mechanisms of development. The histological picture requires differential diagnosis with psoriasis and other dermatoses.

Conclusion

Histological examination is an important method for diagnosing acute guttate parapsoriasis. The identified changes make it possible to confirm the diagnosis and choose the optimal treatment strategy..

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